

NON-DESTRUCTIVE QUALITY ASSESSMENT FOR SEMI-FINISHED TEXTILES

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ABSTRACT

Methods and technologies to efficiently reduce scrape rates with novel non-destructive testing were developed, including material and feature characterisation for multi-ply semi-finished textiles (e.g. stacks, preforms). A set of experiments was completed to investigate the potential of air-flow based quality measurements for feature and defect detection. A new measurement concept for 2D semi-finished textiles is introduced, utilising a set of pressure sensors to determine relative pressure differences between certain ports.

The presented airflow-based methods were developed to provide quality assessment of semi-finished textiles without the need for reference measurements or historical data. These methods were developed to be more independent from the cavity thickness, with a strong focus on fast and simple measurements. The presented techniques compare pressure sensing areas instead of analysing the inlet pressure at the injection port, which heavily depends on the sample fibre volume fraction. This allows easier implementation of the measurement method online, or inline in current production facilities, where the process target thickness cannot be actively controlled, or a specified thickness cannot be guaranteed. If a significant difference between the pressure sensing areas was detected, the sample was assumed to include some form of feature. A comprehensive set of experiments show that the proposed concept is promising. The distributed pressure measurements were able to detect features of different lengths and severity.

1 INTRODUCTION

The detection of material features within multiply semi-finished stacks, in particular for preforms is cumbersome and requires complex technology, which leads to certain issues within an industrial mass production [1]. Common issues encountered in LCM processes are the formation of dry spots, void inclusion and other specific features depending on the chosen method of resin infusion [2]. The implementation and application of quality systems for a highly automated industrial production line to produce high-quality CFRP are still at an early stage. Existing methods to measure these quantities focuses on accurate characterisation for process simulation, are time intensive and laboratory-based and therefore too expensive for utilisation in an industrial environment [3][4]. The use of air flow has been proven to be suitable for material characterisation in a non-destructive manner [5]. Different air-flow based methods are presented within this paper to characterise a multi-ply semi-finished textile, and demonstrate how they can be applied to detect material features. Defect detection within preforms is the focus of this paper.

The presence of defects within multi-ply preforms usually leads to a change of local material properties (e.g. area weight, porosity) which results in local injectability variations. Previous investigations carried out by Hermann et al. were focused on the material and feature characterisation of 2D semi-finished textiles [5][6]. To improve the capabilities of the proposed air-flow based measurement to detect material inhomogeneities within an industrial mass production of CFRP, further methods were developed. Instead of analysing the injection pressures to determine the injectability of textiles, here the relative pressure difference between two pressure sensing areas was analysed.

Figure 1 shows the evolution from the material characterising injectability measurements towards the feature detecting distributed pressure measurements.

The following main questions were addressed:

1. Is the measurement method capable of detecting features?
2. Is the measurement insensitive to target thickness variations?

Figure 1: Locally distributed pressure measurement using alternative measurement heads.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup is presented schematically in Figure 2. Initially, pressurised air passed through a manual pressure regulator and filter unit to clean and regulate the pressurised air from the main supply. Another manual pressure regulator regulated the pressure at the inlet. The inlet pressure was monitored and recorded with a -1 to +1 bar (Festo SPAN-B2R-R18M-PN-PN-L1) pressure sensor. The same sensors were used to record the pressure at the slot cavities within feature detection measurement heads, which act as pressure sensing areas (see Figure 3). The volumetric flow rate and air temperature were monitored before entering the semi-finished textile through the injection slot. Pressure transducers were mounted close to the sample at the inlet and the two sensing ports. Data from the measurement equipment were constantly logged with 100 Hz during each experiment using LabView data acquisition software.

Figure 2: Experimental setup; schematic of the distributed pressure measurement.

In addition, the applied compaction force and the position of the mould platens were recorded using the Instron Bluehill software package. The experimental fixtures and mould platens have been mounted within a 200 kN Instron 1186 UTM.

Figure 3: Experimental setup; distributed pressure measurement.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND MATERIAL CONFIGURATION

The distributed pressure measurements utilised a new type of measurement head design with one slot as an injector in the middle of the head and two pressure sensing ports (see Figure 3). Both experimental streams follow the same basic procedure. The experiments began by placing the sample onto the bottom tool, with the feature always facing to the same pressure port. The samples were compacted to the target thickness before the air was injected subsequently using a steady-state flow. The inlet pressure was manually adjusted. A brief moment of flow stabilisation was given after the injection pressure was reached before the pressure readings were monitored at the right and left slots and the average taken over one second.

The ability to detect features was quantified by comparing the pressures at the left and right port and calculating the relative difference following Eqn. (1):

$$P_{rel} = \sqrt{\left(0.5 - \frac{P_{R/L}}{P_R + P_L}\right)^2} \quad (1)$$

where P_{rel} is the relative pressure difference between the left and right port in percent. Here, left and right were arbitrary selected positions to define whether the pressure sensing port can be found left or right from the injection port. P_R represents the measured pressure at the right port, whereas P_L represents the measured pressure at the left port (both in kPa). $P_{R/L}$ represent either the pressure value recorded at the right or left pressure port. The pressure measured at the left and right port would be equal with a share of 50 % of the sum if a perfect homogeneous material is tested. P_{rel} would be equal to zero in this case. Steady-state measurements utilised the relative pressure difference between sensor one and sensor two as a quality indicator.

The examined test scenarios were related to real production issues, in this case, specified to detect folds in preforms with various characteristics. This included measurements on manipulated samples representing features with different severity. The experimental procedure was subdivided into two different sections.

1. Conceptual validation through experiments
2. Evaluating the influence of target thickness on the measured result

For both investigations, samples were prepared from multiple plies of a 300 g/m² carbon fibre Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) supplied by SGL-ACF and used by BMW within the series production [5][6]. Samples were taken from a fresh roll of NCF. The samples were cut to 100 x 100 mm squares and stacked together forming a nine-layer stack with a symmetric layup (+45/-45/90/0/90/0/90/-45/+45) placing the feature plies after the fifth layer. The artificially introduced features represented material densifications. The type and elongation of the features were chosen based on experience and factors such as replicability and ease of implementation. Folds can lead most likely to dry spots by increasing the local fibre volume fraction (V_f) and decreasing the permeability. Rovings were taken from single plies of NCF with a width of 5 mm to replicate this kind of material densification. The rovings were stapled on a layer of NCF slightly larger than 100 x 100 mm and then added to the normal stack layup. All samples were preformed before testing, the binder being activated by subsequent heating and cooling steps to adhere the sample layers [7]. Samples were conditioned for at least two days to the laboratory environment prior to testing.

4 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Preform specimens were manufactured for both experimental streams. Seven distinctive features were artificially introduced into the specimens, which differed in length and position to simulate folds with distinctive severity. The first type is equivalent to slight densification representing a one-layer fold within the preform, where simply two extra rovings were placed between the layer. The second type is bolder, placing four rovings equivalent to a two-layer fold, between the layers. Features with possibly higher influence on the flow path were not considered as compaction stresses increase exponentially with increasing fibre volume fraction, leading to high compaction forces which could possibly exceed load restrictions arising from the supporting equipment.

For each configuration, each representing a feature preform, five specimens were produced to obtain statistical relevance data. In total, 70 specimens were prepared. Table 1 shows the dimensions and positions of the fold in each preform type. Reference measurements were performed on nine feature-free preforms.

Geometry		Dimensions (in mm)				
	Configuration	a	b	L	x	y
	1	100	100	100	18.75	0
	2	100	100	65	18.75	35
	3	100	100	35	18.75	65
	4	100	100	30	18.75	35
	5	100	100	25	18.75	65
	6	100	100	60	0	20
	7	100	100	60	38.5	20

Table 1: Dimensions of artificially introduced preform features.

4.1 Detectability of Artificially Introduced Features

This set of experiments were designed to demonstrate the capability of the measurement method to detect features within semi-finished textiles, as an initial proof of concept. A schematic overview of all the features introduced into the preform samples is presented in Figure 4. Features were directly placed on the inlet and sensing areas to assess the measurement sensitivity when a feature is potentially blocking the measurements zones. The elongation of the features ranks from small features, which are potentially harder to detect to more pronounced features. Two concepts were tested, investigating the influence of additional edge clamping at the sample periphery to guide the flow and possibly increase the sensitivity of feature detection. Measurements were undertaken with and without additional clamping along the horizontal tool edges. Shims were added to the bottom plate once all the non-guided flow experiments were complete, to investigate guided flow. The guided flow scenario utilised shims with a length of 100 mm, a width of 10 mm and a thickness of 0.3 mm. The shims were positioned perpendicular to the injection slot and along the outer edge, and fixed in position with adhesive tape (0.05 mm thickness).

Figure 4: Overview of the types of artificially introduced preform features.

A paired, two-tailed t-test was chosen to study the significance of the gathered results. The measured pressure differences between the sensing ports should be significant and proof that the measurement method can detect features. A null hypothesis was proposed, stating that the introduced features influenced the measured pressure at the sensing areas. The pressure at the sensing areas must be different. A standard p-value higher than 0.05 rejects the null-hypothesis and proves that different pressures measured at the sensing areas are not significant.

4.2 Evaluating the Influence of Target Thickness

This study was designed to quantify the sensitivity of the measurement method to thickness variations, for scenarios in which the target thickness cannot be actively controlled, or lower clamping force requirements are established by measuring at higher sample thicknesses.

Each specimen was placed onto the bottom tool and compressed to the target thickness. The compression cycle started with the lowest target V_f . Each specimen was tested for 15 target thicknesses. Each thickness corresponded to a certain fibre volume fraction ranging from 45 % to 59 % and altered in 1 % intervals as presented in Table 2. At each thickness, air was injected at a constant injection pressure of 90 kPa through the injection port. The response at both sensing port on the left and right side of the measurement head was recorded, and the sample subsequently compressed to the next V_f . Here, only preforms with feature configuration one and four were examined (see Section 4.1).

V_f (%)	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59
Target Thickness (mm)	3.60	3.52	3.44	3.37	3.30	3.24	3.17	3.11	3.05	3.00	2.94	2.89	2.84	2.79	2.74

Table 2: Fibre volume fractions and corresponding target thicknesses for sensitivity study.

Feature one should be easy to detect, whereas feature four being smaller, was expected to be significantly harder to detect. Five specimens of each preform type, referred to as a configuration, were tested to gain statistically relevant results. Reference measurements were conducted on nine samples to assess any influence arising from the tool alignment. The reference measurements should demonstrate if the sensing ports show any bias. A correction can be applied if any noticeable tendency is measured.

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

5.1 Detectability of Artificially Introduced Features

Figure 5 presents the experimental results for the non-guided, steady-state flow experiments for two types of tested features (type-1, one-layer fold layer and type-2, two-layer fold layer). The feature configuration axis in this figure represents the artificially introduced features as presented in Section 4. Feature configuration 1, 2, 6 and 7 generated good differentiation of measured pressures at the sensing areas. The features directly positioned at the inlet (6) or the sensing areas (7) showed a higher standard deviation. Those deviations were expected due to the dimension of the feature (the feature's width is similar to the slot's width) and position inaccuracies within the stack and preform itself on the measurement head. The feature configurations with type-2 features (four rovings) showed a more distinct result than feature configurations with type-1 features. The pressure difference between the sensing ports was notably higher for feature configuration 1, 2 and 6.

Figure 5: Measured pressure ratios for steady-state, non-guided flow.

Comparing feature configuration 2 with feature configuration 3 reveals a contradictory pattern for type-2 features. Feature configuration 2 should provide a pressure ratio higher than feature configuration 3, due to its pronounced length. Unfortunately, the experimental results could not confirm this expected behaviour. The pressure ratio for feature configuration 3 was noticeable higher than feature configuration 2. Feature configuration 2 was identified as an outlier for type-2 features. The pressure ratio for feature configuration 6 is relatively high, and could have arisen from inaccurate placement of

the features within the preform or the placement of the preform itself on the tool. Figure 6 presents the results for the guided flow case. The trend was very similar to the non-guided steady-state flow case with a slight decrease in the pressure ratio between the sensing areas.

Figure 6: Measured pressure ratio for steady-state, guided flow.

The reference measurements are presented in Figure 7 and were all conducted on nine specimens without features. The average pressure difference between the left and the right port was 3.12%. This value acted as a support for the chosen p-value of 0.05. The significance study proved that most of the configurations show a significant difference between the measured pressures. The null hypothesis only got rejected for a specific combination of configuration 5 and 7 (see Table 2).

The results presented in Figures 5 to 7 have proved that the proposed measurement method can detect the presence of features and material densification, for most of the introduced features. Material features placed directly on top of the sensing areas and injection port (feature configuration 6 and 7) showed a high expected variation and could not be detected with the required confidence. Features with small elongation were also not traceable (stack configuration 5). The experimental results showed clearly noticeable pressure differences between the left and right sensing ports in this case, but not within the required statistical significance. Nonetheless, the proposed measurement method was able to detect material features within multi-ply preforms. For most of the investigated cases, the pressure sensing ports showed significant results with p-values smaller than 0.01.

The hypothesis that additional clamping along preform edges “guides” the flow and results in better feature detectability could be rejected. The influence of additional clamping was shown to have a minor influence on the measurement results.

Figure 7: Reference measurements; Pressure difference between left and right port.

Guide	Non-Guided		Guided	
Config.	1-Fold	2-Fold	1-Fold	2-Fold
1	0.013	0.000	0.022	0.000
2	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.000
3	0.004	0.000	0.019	0.000
4	0.016	0.001	0.021	0.000
5	0.106	0.068	0.454	0.068
6	0.015	0.004	0.024	0.012
7	0.006	0.143	0.003	0.133

Table 2: Significance study for feature detection, for the non-guided and guided flow cases.

5.2 Evaluating the Influence of Target Thickness

The aim of the second experimental study was to prove that the measurement method can detect features with varying target thickness, supporting an industrial implementation where specific thickness values cannot be guaranteed, and a robust quality measurement method is required. Figure 8 (a) presents the relative pressure difference between the ports for feature preform one (two-layer folds) with increasing V_f . This data reveals that a decrease of V_f led to a decreasing detectability of the feature, as the relative pressure difference between the sensing ports also decreased. The pressure ratio gradually increased with increasing V_f , and tended to level off. Experiments with higher V_f to confirm this behaviour, were not conducted due to load restrictions occurring from the fixture. The measurement showed the lowest ratio between the sensing ports at the lowest V_f (45 % at 3.60 mm) with 26.45 % (as defined by Eqn. (1)). This ratio increased until the highest V_f was reached (59 % at 2.74 mm) resulting in a pressure ratio of 45.08 %. The plotted graph follows an s-shape. The slope at lower V_f increases and decreases with higher V_f . The permeability value along the flow path through the artificial defect seems to increase non-linear and not as much as the permeability value along the edges close to the inlet (where no defect is present).

A t-test was performed on the results showing that all measured values were significantly different from each other. The p-values for feature preform one are visualised in Figure 8 (b). For illustrative reasons, the threshold is not shown in the figure. It is clear that probability values for all tested V_f were far below the 5 % threshold, ranging from 0.0001 % at 49 % V_f to 0.01 % at 57 % V_f . Although the values were very low, an increase with decrease in target thickness was noticeable. This increase might have been caused by errors such as the possibility of deformation of the mount that might have led to a slight inaccuracy of the recorded target thickness. In other words, the measurement results were still to a small extent dependent on the V_f . Nonetheless, the feature was detectable throughout the tested range of V_f .

Figure 8: Pressure ratio (a) and p-value (b) for feature preform one (two-layer fold).

Figure 9 (a) presents the relative pressure difference between the ports for feature preform four. Here, a two-layer fold only ranged from the bottom of the specimen 35 mm towards the top. The smaller footprint influenced the measurement results in an expected manner. The ability to detect defects significantly decreased. The evolution of the plotted pressure ratio and target thickness revealed an almost linear behaviour with an increasing trend towards higher V_f with a slight deviation for the two lowest V_f (at 3.60 mm and 3.52 mm). Here, the permeability along the flow path through the feature increases linearly with a higher rate than the permeability value along the edges close to the inlet. An increase of V_f led to a decreasing pressure difference between the sensing ports. An assessment of the t-test results presented in Figure 9 (b) revealed that a reliable defect detection required V_f 's higher than 48 %. The p-value for V_f lower than 48 % surpassed the threshold indicating that the measured results were not significantly different from each other. Generally, measurements still showed a noticeable pressure difference between the sensing areas indicate, but the combination of low-pressure ratios and high p-values led to the assumption that features could not reliably be detected at low V_f . P-values were high for low V_f and dropped exponentially with increasing V_f .

Figure 9: Pressure ratio (a) and p-value (b) for feature preform four (two-layer fold).

It can be concluded that an increase in V_f , and the related decrease in target thickness, improved the detectability of a feature for the presented showcases. Nevertheless, small features like those represented in preform four reached a relative pressure difference between the sensing port of 9.3 % at a V_f of 59 %, whereas preform one with a distinctive feature showed a pressure difference at the sensing port of 26.45 % at V_f of only 45 %. This was expected as smaller features do not obstruct the air flow to the same extent as the elongated fold, thus pressure differences at the sensing ports were smaller, even at higher V_f . With increasing V_f the average permeability of the sample within the measurement zone decreases, which leads to a flow rate reduction and therefore a local pressure reduction at the pressure sensing ports.

In general, smaller differences between the sensing ports at different V_f led to higher p-values. It should be noted that the very low compaction forces at lower V_f may have allowed air to escape along the surface of the preform, instead of flowing through it. The limit for accurate measurements was found at 48 % V_f for feature preform four. Below this value, the p-value surpassed the threshold of 5 % for significance. The significance value for feature preform one did not drop below this threshold for any tested V_f . The required clamping forces should also be considered as an increase in fibre volume fraction led to higher compaction forces. The required force for the compaction of the specimens of feature preform one at the lowest target thickness of 2.74 mm reached values up to 11.46 kN. The maximum recorded compaction force for preform feature four was 5.65 kN. A minimum of compaction force of 220 N for feature preform four and 401.2 N for feature preform one was measured at the critical V_f of 48 %. This data reinforced the expected result that the size of the fold drastically influences the required compaction force.

6 CONCLUSIONS

A novel measurement method was presented for non-destructive material characterisation and feature detection within semi-finished textiles. Instead of focusing on material characterisation, in this paper the detection of features is the central aspect. A new measurement concept for 2D semi-finished textiles was introduced, utilising a set of pressure sensors to determine relative pressure differences between certain ports.

The presented experiments and results have shown that the proposed concept is promising. The distributed pressure measurements were able to detect features with different elongation and severity. The influence of target thickness on the measurement results was identified and quantified. Here, valuable information on the force versus target thickness relationship was obtained, to provide guidelines for an appropriate clamping mechanism. These findings led to the definition of the optimal operational target thickness, sensitive enough to detect defects without imposing too much clamping force. In this context the usage of additional edge clamping was investigated.

However, the concept was still sensitive to certain features independent of the sample target thickness and V_f . Higher compaction forces generally improved the sensitivity of the measurement method. Reliable results were only measurable for V_f greater than 48 %. If measurements are conducted at V_f close to 48 % compaction forces are relatively low, and could be easily supplied by a physical measurement system. Any further increase in V_f will increase the compaction force which should be considered in terms of tool deflection, measurement accuracy and technical design. The preferred V_f during the measurement depends ultimately on the application. The proposed measurement method was able to detect features, at least within a specified range of V_f . It has been proven, that historical data is not required to detect features and flaws within semi-finished textiles. However, features and flaws should be located between the ports. Features directly placed at the inlet or sensing ports, were difficult to detect if only the pressure difference between the ports is considered as an indicator. Such abnormalities can be traced if the flow rate of air is monitored during the measurement, and comparisons made from sample to sample, leading to the requirement for historical data.

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